

First report of scuttle fly, *Megaselia scalaris* (Loew, 1866) (Diptera: Phoridae) as a facultative endoparasitoid of Bombay locust (Orthoptera)

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Abstract

The present study reports *Megaselia scalaris* (Loew, 1866) as a facultative endoparasitoid of the Bombay locust, *Patanga cf. succincta* (Johannson, 1763) for the first time. This case of parasitism was observed inside the insect box where the recently collected locust was stored. The life cycle of the scuttle fly, which was studied till the adult emergence, is described. The results of this study may help us to understand *M. scalaris* as the natural enemy of the Bombay locust. It may also generate fresh concepts for integrated pest management strategies.

Key words: endoparasitoid; phorid fly; Bombay locust; maggots; forensic entomology.

Introduction

Scuttle fly also called as phorid fly, humpbacked fly, or coffin fly, is a cosmopolitan fly known for its rapid and jerky movement. These flies are small measuring between 0.5–6 mm in length, and generally resemble fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) in appearance. But scuttle flies lack the red eye that is the classic feature of the fruit fly. When viewed from the side, there is a pronounced hump to the thorax of these scuttle flies. Being omnivorous, the scuttle fly *M. scalaris* can inhabit a wide range of habitats and ecological niches. The immature stages of this species are reported as detritivore, parasite, parasitoid, phytophagous, and coprophagous (Tumrasvin *et al.*, 1977; Koller *et al.*, 2003; Disney, 2008). The adult is reported as polyphagous, feasting on a wide range of food (Chakraborty *et al.*, 2016). Scuttle flies are important in forensic entomology due to their necrophagous behaviour. In the insect succession pattern on the carcass, these flies, are a secondary coloniser of the carcass, and can become primary colonisers in mechanically barricaded environments (Chakraborty *et al.*, 2016). Hence the maggots of the phorid flies are generally used for estimation of Post Mortem Interval (PMI). The parasitoid nature of this fly larvae is due to overcrowding (Chakraborty *et al.*, 2016). This scuttle fly can feed on a wide variety of living arthropods: Orthoptera (Gregorio & Leonide, 1980), Diptera (Batista-Da-Silva, 2012), Lepidoptera (Rajan & Shamsudeen, 2023), Coleoptera (Harrison & Gardner, 1991; Binsha *et al.*, 2020), Hymenoptera (Zanon, 1991), Hemiptera (El-Hawagry *et al.*, 2021), and Araneae (Disney, 1994). It is also reported to feed on inedible materials like shoe polish or paint (Lever, 1944; McCrae, 1967).

Among the above-mentioned hosts, some are major economic pests on the crops, and hence, there is a possibility of utilising *M. scalaris* as a biological control agent in Integrated Pest Management. It has also been reported as a laboratory pest, infesting invertebrate culture in labs: cockroaches (Robinson, 1975), flies (Zwart *et al.*, 2005), etc. It is reported to infest praying mantis (Orthoptera) (Koch *et al.*, 2013) and, as a facultative endoparasite, of various hosts: cockroaches, crickets, beetles (El-Hawagry, 2021), and grasshoppers: *Tettigonia viridissima* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Zonocerus variegatus* (Linnaeus, 1758), and *Sphenarium purpurascens* Charpentier, 1842 (Gregorio & Leonide, 1980; Quesada-Béjar *et al.*, 2017) etc. To our knowledge there are no reports of these flies' infesting locusts.

Locusts are the short-horned grasshoppers with migratory habits, marked polymorphism, and voracious feeding behaviour (Singh *et al.*, 2023). The congregation of adults is known as swarms, and nymphal congregation is hopper bands. The swarms are reported to migrate hundreds of kilometres per day (Singh *et al.*, 2023), invading areas covering millions of square kilometres. The swarm causes major economic, social, and environmental impacts on an international scale. In 1970, when Bombay locust seriously invaded Thailand, the aerial doses of insecticides failed to control it. The government declared locusts as a food rich in protein and since then it has become the delicious favourite street food in Thailand. Bombay locusts are used as delicious food in many Asian countries (e.g., Thailand, China, Japan, Philippines, Vietnam, India, Laos, Malaysia and Myanmar); South America (e.g., Mexico); and Europe (e.g., Ukraine and Belgium) (Yhoung-Aree, 2010; Costa-Neto & Dunkel, 2016; Mitsuhashi, 2016; Poma *et al.*, 2017; Egonyu *et al.*, 2021). A large swarm of Bombay locusts may cause crop damage ranging from 80% to 100% (Brader *et al.*, 2006). The swarms of locusts are difficult to control using pesticides alone, and hence Integrated Pest Management using parasites, predators, pathogens and insecticides may help in managing the swarms in a better way.

Here we present the first report of *M. scalaris* as a facultative endoparasitoid of the Bombay locust. This finding may contribute to our understanding of *M. scalaris* host range and emphasize the need for additional research into the use of *M. scalaris* to control the Bombay locust.

Materials and methods

One specimen of Bombay locust identified as *Patanga* cf. *succincta* (Johannson, 1763) using available literature (Kirby, 1914; Chand *et al.*, 2022), was collected from the campus of the Zoological Survey of India, Western Regional Centre, Pune (ZSI-WRC). It was stored in the fumigated entomological box. The following day, some maggots were seen emerging from the locust's body (Fig. 1A). Immediately the locust, along with the maggots, was transferred to a separate transparent jar to monitor the development of the maggots inside it (Fig. 2A). The mouth of the jar was tied with muslin cloth for proper aeration.

The presence and survival of maggots, pupae and new adults was monitored on a daily basis. The duration of each stage (larval, pupal, and adult) and morphometric data was recorded (Table 1–2). The number of larvae and their developmental stages were studied and photographed under Leica S9i stereomicroscope till the adult stage. The figure plates were prepared using Adobe Photoshop version 2008.

The adult flies, maggots and pupa were identified using Chakraborty *et al.* (2013). For rearing the flies in the laboratory, two different kinds of food were offered: i) fish food and ii) overripe bananas. The flies avoided fish food and instead favored overripe bananas.

Morphometric Analysis Using PAST Specimen Measurement and Data Preparation

A total of six specimens (MS1–MS6) were measured for 12 morphometric characters (Table 2), including body length, frontal width, eye length and width, thorax width and length, abdomen length and width, ovipositor length, wing width and length, and hind tibia length. All measurements were taken using a calibrated stereomicroscope and recorded in millimeters (mm).

Table 2. Morphometric data of *Megaselia scalaris* (Loew, 1866)

Fly individual s	Body length	Frontal width	Eye length	Eye width	Thorax width	Thorax length	Abdomen length	Abdomen width	Ovipositor length	Wing width	Wing length	Hind tibia length
MS1	2.48	0.61	0.36	0.25	0.64	0.59	1.57	0.92	0.37	0.80	1.77	0.71
MS2	2.26	0.54	0.35	0.23	0.56	0.55	1.32	0.73	0.07	0.65	1.66	0.63
MS3	2.23	0.59	0.37	0.25	0.61	0.67	1.28	0.75	0.81	0.80	1.76	0.70
MS4	2.07	0.56	0.38	0.24	0.61	0.60	1.34	0.52	0.06	0.88	1.83	0.65
MS5	2.14	0.54	0.32	0.21	0.54	0.44	1.41	0.57	0.12	0.71	1.61	0.62

MS6	1.75	0.52	0.30	0.19	0.56	0.65	0.95	0.43	0.05	0.70	1.57	0.67
Mean	2.155	0.56	0.346	0.228	0.586	0.583	1.311	0.653	0.246	0.756	1.7	0.663

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

To identify major axes of variation among specimens, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed using the correlation matrix (as measurements were in different units/scales). PCA reduced the dimensionality of the dataset and allowed visualization of group clustering and variable contributions. The first two principal components (PC1 and PC2) were retained and plotted to interpret the morphometric variation.

Correlation Analysis

A Pearson correlation matrix was generated to explore relationships among the 12 morphometric variables. This helped identify which characters were strongly correlated and contributed most to variation.

All analyses were conducted in PAST version 5.2.2, which is freely available (Hammer *et al.*, 2001). A one-way ANOVA (Table 4) was conducted to assess whether there were significant differences in PC1 and PC2 scores between two groups (Group 1: MS1–MS3, Group 2: MS4–MS6).

Abbreviations: MS – *Megaselia scalaris*; msp – *Megaselia scalaris* pupa.

Results

The present study was taken up with an objective to present a first report of *M. scalaris* as a facultative endoparasitoid of Bombay locust. In this study the life cycle of *M. scalaris* was also studied in the laboratory conditions.

1) Identification of the facultative endoparasitoid

Order: Diptera Linnaeus, 1758

Superfamily: Platypezoidea Fallén, 1815

Family: Phoridae Curtis, 1833

Subfamily: Metopininae Peterson, 1887

Genus *Megaselia* Rondani, 1856

***Megaselia scalaris* (Loew, 1866)** (Figs 1–2).

Material examined: 40ex, WRC, ZSI, Pune, Maharashtra, 15.i.2025, A.S. Kalawate (ZSI, WRC, Ent.10/276).

2) Identification of the host

Order: Orthoptera Latreille, 1793

Suborder: Caelifera Ander, 1939

Family: Acrididae MacLeay, 1819

Genus *Patanga* Uvarov, 1923

***Patanga cf. succincta* (Johannson, 1763)** (Figs 1D–E).

Material examined: 01ex, WRC campus, ZSI, Pune, Maharashtra, 20.xii.2024, A.S. Kalawate (ZSI, WRC, Ent.5/1795).

3) Partial Life cycle study of *M. scalaris* in the lab

Rearing. The maggots collected from the locust were reared in the laboratory for further observations (Figs. 1A and 2A). Since the scuttle fly is an endoparasitoid, it lay eggs in the locust's hemocoel, making them invisible to the naked eye (Figs 1F–G, 2A–B), and hence eggs were not observed in the present study. The pupal stage remained for 9 days, and before the adult emergence, the pupae changed their colour from pale yellow to blackish. Forty of the forty-five pupae were able to mature into adults, which lasted for nine days (Figs 2C–G). The details of the life cycle study are given in Table 1 and Figs 1 & 2.

In this study, *M. scalaris* is reported to infest the Bombay locust for the first time.

Table 1. Observation of *Megaselia scalaris* (Loew, 1866) larvae to adult stage

Life stages	Number of Individuals	Duration	Temperature (Minimum and Maximum)
Maggots	97	4 days (25/12/2024 to 28/12/2024)	16-32 °C
Pupation	45	9 days (29/12/2024 to 06/01/2025)	14-32 °C
Adult	40	9 days (07/01/2025 to 15/01/2025)	13-30 °C

Figure 1. A, Maggots were coming out of the body of the Bombay locust; B, Phorid fly emergence; C, Rearing flies in the laboratory with different foods; D–E, *Patanga cf. succinata* (Johannson, 1763); F–G, Pupal case on *Patanga cf. succinata* (Johannson, 1763).

Figure 2. A, Maggots with Bombay locust in the transparent jar; B, Maggots; C–D, Pupal stages; E, Emergence of adult phorid fly; F–G, *Megaselia scalaris* (Loew, 1866).

4) Morphology of the preserved specimens

Maggots (Fig. 2B) were white, cylindrical, with characteristic black mouth hook, and a set of spiracles anteriorly and posteriorly.

Pupae (Figs 2C–E) Intersegmental spines along the dorsal and lateral segments, as well as the sculpture of the pupal respiratory horn, are characteristics of the *M. scalaris* pupa. The pupal stage lasted nine days in this study.

Adult (Figs 2E–G) stage characterized by the presence of the humpbacked and legs with flattened hind femora lasted for nine days.

All the specimens were females, so we could not get the F1 generation and couldn't repeat the cycle.

5) Morphometric Analysis Using PAST

To investigate patterns of morphometric variation, we performed a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using values for 12 body characters. The scree plot illustrating the eigenvalues of each principal component, presented in Figure 3. The results indicated that the first principal component (PC1) accounted for approximately 62% of the total variance, while the second component (PC2) explained an additional 27%. Together, these two components captured approximately 89% of the total variance in the dataset (Table 3). In Fig. 3, a clear inflection point, or “elbow,” was observed after the second component, beyond which the eigenvalues dropped sharply and contributed minimally to the overall variance (each below 10%). PC1 was heavily influenced by body length, abdomen length, and wing length, indicating that size variation is a major source of morphometric differentiation. PC2 was more associated with ovipositor length and thorax length. The PCA plot (Figure 3) revealed that specimen MS6 was distinct from others, suggesting the developmental differentiation due to laboratory conditions.

Figure 3. PCA Scree Plot.

Table 3. PCA table with eigenvalues and variance

Components	Eigenvalue	% variance
PC1	0.134389	63.669
PC 2	0.0553464	26.221
PC 3	0.0134046	6.3506
PC 4	0.00672909	3.188
PC 5	0.00120646	0.57158
PC 6	1.30596E-07	6.1872E-05

To evaluate whether the morphometric measurements significantly differed between the two groups, a one-way ANOVA (Table 4) was performed on the first two principal components (PC1 and PC2), which together explained 89.89% of the total variance. The analysis did not reveal any statistically significant differences between groups for PC1 ($F(1, 4) = 2.80$, $p = 0.166$) or PC2 ($F(1, 4) = 0.12$, $p = 0.751$). Two types of hypotheses are tested here: Null Hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant difference in the PCA scores (PC1 and PC2) between the two groups and Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): There is a significant difference in the PCA scores between the two groups. These results fail to reject the null hypothesis,

suggesting that the morphometric variation captured by the first two principal components is not significantly structured by group membership.

Table 4. One-way ANOVA for morphometric data

Principal Component	F-value	df (between, within)	p-value	Significance
PC1	2.80	(1,4)	0.166	Not significant
PC2	0.12	(1,4)	0.751	Not significant

6) Stages and duration

The length of time from maggots to the adult stage was documented in order to observe how long the life stages lasted in response to temperature variations (Fig. 2, Table 1). At Max 32°C and Min 16°C the maggots took 4 days before pupation. The pupal life at Max 32°C and Min 14°C was about 9 days. Thus, at Max 32°C and Min 14°C the life cycle was completed in about 13 days.

Discussion

This report presents the first documented evidence of *M. scalaris* acting as a facultative endoparasitoid of the Bombay locust. It highlights the complex interactions between insects in tropical ecosystems. Till this study, there are no reports or literature available of endoparasitism of locusts by this scuttle fly. The dietary habit of scuttle fly is varied from saprophagous parasitic to necrophagous, and they have even been reported feeding on inedible materials.

When aerial insecticide spraying fails to control the Bombay locust swarms, which cause economic harm to any nation, the use of this scuttle fly as part of an integrated pest management plan may be helpful. Hence, the potential of *M. scalaris* as a biological control agent needs to be further investigated in detail. Biological control efforts are focused on specific parasitoids and predators, whereas *M. scalaris* may represent an example of a generalist saprophage that has evolved the ability to occasionally exploit a live host (Acevedo-Alcalá, 2023). The potential uses of scuttle flies as biological control agents should be explored, including their efficacy and safety in regulating orthopteran populations. The population dynamics of Bombay locusts and *M. scalaris* should be studied in more detail to understand the cascading effects of the parasitic relationship on ecosystem processes.

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